

WIUT students' opinions about the effectiveness of MyBib for source references of coursework.

Abstract

Many WIUT students use MyBib to reference and cite sources for their coursework. However, despite its popularity, a review of academic papers revealed a lack of research into MyBib's effectiveness. Therefore, the objective of this research was to analyze WIUT students' opinions on the effectiveness of MyBib for referencing. Research was conducted through an online questionnaire posted on numerous WIUT telegram groups. A total of 33 students completed the questionnaire about MyBib where they compared it with other reference managers. An analysis of responses showed that most students found MyBib easy to use and satisfactory. This study found that male students generally consider MyBib effective, while most female students find it ineffective. Such diversion of opinions suggests that user experience with this tool can be influenced significantly by gender. For this reason, further research is needed to better understand MyBib's effectiveness across diverse populations.

Keywords: MyBib, reference management software, reference manager, referencing tools, citation, reference tool, referencing.

Introduction

Researchers heavily rely on referencing to avoid plagiarism and give credit to sources they have used. However, referencing usually is not seen as an intellectually stimulating task; instead, it is often regarded as a routine obligation with strict predefined standards. With the introduction of referencing software, many researchers choose to delegate this task to digital tools, which tend to perform fast and accurately, allowing them to focus more on the intellectual aspects of their work. The existence of multiple citation and referencing styles, as well as the increased number of sources that researchers need to reference for their work, has further encouraged the use of referencing tools.

Such reliance on referencing tools highlights the need to evaluate which reference managers are most effective. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to analyze the opinions of WIUT students on the effectiveness of MyBib, a reference manager, for referencing coursework. This research attempted to analyze the responses of 33 WIUT students regarding their opinions about MyBib and how it compares to other reference managers.

Literature Review

Researchers use a variety of referencing tools, but most academic studies focused on reference managers such as EndNote and Zotero. This literature review explores the differences between these two tools and how university students engage with reference management software.

EndNote and Zotero

Many researchers consider EndNote and Zotero to be two of the best reference management tools (Ivey and Crum, 2018, p425). EndNote is known for its advanced features, such as automatic bibliography generation using the given citation information (Ivey and Crum, 2018, p402). Compared to Zotero, EndNote also has the advantage of merging two or more citations into one field (Rakhshan, 2012, p158). Additionally, Rakhshan's findings suggest that EndNote offers a more user-friendly interface for changing citation styles than Zotero. However, researchers Ray and Ramesh (2017, p241) support the use of Zotero, arguing that as free and open-source software, Zotero has numerous benefits. For example, Zotero can be run as an offline database and function without a constant internet connection. Another advantage is that it can extract metadata from PDF files (Ray and Ramesh, 2017, p. 235). Nonetheless, they admit that Zotero is not without drawbacks. Unlike EndNote, Zotero cannot automatically remove duplicate items and does not offer many referencing styles (Ray and Ramesh, 2017, p. 215). Both EndNote and Zotero have different strengths and weaknesses, and the user's choice depends on personal preferences.

University students' engagement with reference management software

Research shows that university students have a low level of engagement with reference management software. Salem and Fehrman (2013, cited in Awang et al., 2019, p. 6) found that few undergraduate students use citation managers, and some are unwilling to use them, preferring to do their citing and referencing manually. Another study by Lee (2020) suggests that many students at the University of Central Florida struggle with citation and do not know how to cite properly. His findings indicate that the majority of students do not know about or use citation management software. Overall, Salem, Fehrman, and Lee found that students either have difficulty using reference management tools or are not familiar or comfortable with them (2013, cited in Awang et al., 2019; 2020).

Academic literature review showed no studies on MyBib. Therefore, the current research examines WIUT students' opinions about the effectiveness of using MyBib, a reference management tool, for referencing and citing research articles.

Methods

Overview

This chapter discusses the participants of the study, the data collection method, the justification for the chosen research instrument, and ethical considerations.

Research participants

The research participants were thirty-three randomly selected undergraduate students from Westminster International University in Tashkent, consisting of ten females and twenty-three males (Appendix B, Figures 1), with an age range of 16 to 22 (Appendix B, Figures 2).

Regarding their level of study, twenty-three students were at Level 3, five were at Level 4, and two identified themselves as Level 6 (Appendix B, Figure 3).

Ethical considerations

The students were informed of the research's purpose, and their responses were kept strictly confidential to ensure anonymity. Participants' responses were only used for research purposes.

Research instrument

An online questionnaire was used to collect data. Two main justifications for this method were consistency and convenience for the respondents. Consistency was ensured as the same questions were asked in the same way for all respondents, and personal bias or interpretation of the questions did not influence the data. Additionally, respondents could complete the questionnaire at their convenience. The questionnaire consisted of thirteen questions divided into three sections, with demographic questions in the first section (Appendix A, 1-3), questions about

students' experiences with MyBib in the second section (Appendix A, 4-10), and questions about other reference management tools in the last section (Appendix A, 11-13). The questionnaire types included demographic, multiple-choice, Likert scale, yes/no, and mixed questions. The Google form was distributed to WIUT-specific telegram groups with instructions to gather data.

Results

The purpose of this study was to determine whether MyBib effectively helped students with referencing and citation. Specifically, our aim was to investigate whether students who used MyBib achieved their desired results for the referencing component of coursework criteria. In this section, we will present the results of our study in detail.

Students' opinions about MyBib's effectiveness

	strongly agree	agree	neutral	disagree	strongly disagree
males	11%	56%	28%	5%	0%
females	0%	20%	20%	40%	20%

Overall, of the students who used MyBib, 11% of male respondents strongly agreed with the statement that MyBib is effective, while none of the female respondents strongly agreed. Only 20% of women agreed with the proposed statement, whereas the overwhelming 56% of their male counterparts agreed that MyBib is effective. The percentages of males and females who were neutral were almost identical, at 28% and 20%, respectively. Merely 5% of males considered MyBib to be ineffective, while the figure for females who disagreed or strongly disagreed that MyBib is an effective referencing tool was high, at 60%.

Usage and discovery of MyBib

Just under 70% of respondents used MyBib at least once to create source references (Appendix B, Figure 4). The proportion of students who learned about MyBib through WIUT social media was about 35%, whereas students who learned from other WIUT students constituted almost 70% (Appendix B, Figure 5).

Ease of use

When students were asked to describe how easy it was to use MyBib for referencing, about 70% of them considered it easy. The percentage of students who found MyBib difficult to use was about 17%, while 13% of students remained neutral (Appendix B, Figure 6).

Perceived accuracy

As for the accuracy of MyBib, almost 43% of respondents thought that MyBib was accurate, and about 9% of students believed that MyBib had accuracy problems. The proportion of students who were neutral about its accuracy was around 48% (Appendix B, Figure 7).

Impact on grades and overall satisfaction

The survey shows that the proportions of participants achieving a high score and those who received lower scores for the referencing part of the assessment criteria after using MyBib were the same (almost 35%) (Appendix B, Figure 9). Finally, regarding the overall level of satisfaction of students with MyBib, about 48% of respondents were satisfied with MyBib, while around 17% of students expressed dissatisfaction with this reference manager (Appendix B, Figure 10).

Comparison with Other Reference Managers

44% of students who used MyBib reported using other reference managers too (Appendix B, Figure 11). 60% of them used Mendeley, followed by RefWorks at 30%. The proportions of students using RefWorks and those who stated they had used Zotero were the same, at 20% (Appendix B, Figure 12). When respondents were asked to compare other reference managers they had used to MyBib, 70% of students reported that there were no differences, whereas the remaining 30% preferred other reference tools to MyBib (Appendix B, Figure 13).

These findings indicate that many WIUT students consider MyBib easy to use and satisfactory overall, whereas perception of its effectiveness differs significantly by gender. A notable portion of students have tried alternative software, although the majority believe there are no differences.

Discussion

The aim of this section is to discuss the findings in relation to research aim and existing literature, highlighting key insights, patterns and areas for further research. The focus of this study was on whether WIUT students believe MyBib is an effective reference management software. The findings revealed a contrast in perception of MyBib's effectiveness across genders. This is surprising because we did not expect to see such a variation in the opinions of the two genders on this seemingly neutral topic. This discrepancy could be attributed to individual learning preferences or prior experience with digital tools. However, further research is required to explore this relationship.

Our research shows that most students have used reference managers. This finding seems to contradict the results of Salem and Fehrman's (2013) and Lee's (2020) studies, as they reported that only a small number of undergraduate students used reference management software.

Another important finding is that most students became familiar with MyBib with the help of WIUT social media and other WIUT students, which is surprising since the university library, whose main concern is to help students with proper referencing and citation, was expected to be the main factor. The reason for this finding is not clear, but it may have something to do with students' greater engagement with social media and other students and less familiarity with the library and its services.

It was also found that the majority of students believe that MyBib is easy to use for referencing, probably because of its user-friendly interface and constant guides for new users.

Although many students think that MyBib is accurate, a large proportion of respondents were neutral about its accuracy. This large percentage of neutral responses is likely related to the fact that students tend to fully trust a reference manager, and as a result, they might not have checked its accuracy.

Surprisingly, the proportion of students who think MyBib helped them achieve a high score for the referencing component of their coursework and those who do not think so were the same.

This contradiction may be due to how well students use the referencing tool. For example,

students could receive a low score because they did not enter the necessary information that MyBib required, and consequently, they might have referenced their sources incorrectly.

Finally, it was found that most students were satisfied with MyBib (see Appendix B, Figure 10).

A comparison of MyBib with other reference managers revealed that most students believe MyBib is similar to other tools, while the rest of the students think that other reference management software is superior to MyBib. From this, it can be concluded that MyBib and other reference tools are mostly the same and have different strengths and weaknesses, which agrees with the findings of other researchers (Rakhshan, 2012, p. 158; Ray and Ramesh, 2017, p. 241)

Although our study provides important insights into WIUT students' perceptions of the effectiveness of MyBib, there are some limitations to our research that should be noted. Firstly, our sample size was relatively small, and therefore the opinions of the sample may not adequately represent the opinions of all WIUT students. Secondly, the research topic we chose is new, as MyBib has only been in use for a few years. For this reason, there has not been any research done on this specific topic before. Finally, our respondents may not have filled out the questionnaire as truthfully as they should. Despite these limitations, our study remains valid and contributes to a growing body of research on the effectiveness of MyBib.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to explore the perceptions of WIUT students regarding the effectiveness of MyBib as a reference source manager, considering factors such as accuracy and its comparison with other reference software. The findings indicated that most male WIUT students believe that MyBib is effective, whereas the majority of female students reported it to be ineffective. The study also showed that MyBib is easy to use for most students, and the majority of students expressed satisfaction with it. Additionally, the study confirmed that most students perceive MyBib to be similar to other reference managers. In conclusion, MyBib appears to be effective according to male students' perspectives, while female students tend to consider it ineffective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to improve the effectiveness of MyBib as a source reference manager. Firstly, it would be worthwhile to investigate the reasons behind the perceived ineffectiveness of MyBib among female students. Conducting surveys among female students could help to identify any specific issues or challenges they face while using the software. Addressing these issues could help to increase overall satisfaction levels among female students.

Another recommendation is that more research should be conducted to investigate the advantages and disadvantages of using MyBib, as well as its effectiveness. There has been little research done on this topic, so further investigation could provide valuable insights.

Finally, it would be beneficial to conduct further research on other reference managers and compare them with MyBib. This would help to provide greater context to the findings of this study. Overall, these recommendations could contribute to a better understanding of MyBib and other referencing tools.

Reference List

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Appendix A

Questionnaire questions:

1. What is your gender?*

Male

Female

2. What is your age?

*

16-18

19-21

22-24

3. What is your level?

*

Level 3

Level 4

Level 5

Level 6

4. Have you used MyBib to create source references and citation for university assignments? *

Yes

No

5. How did you learn about MyBib?

You can choose more than one option

*

Westminster social media

LRC website

Witut students

Other:

6. On a scale 1-5, how easy is it to use MyBib?

*

Very difficult

1

2

3

4

5

Very easy

7. On a scale 1-5, how would you assess the accuracy of MyBib for referencing and citation?

*

Very inaccurate

1

2

3

4

5

Very accurate

8. Do you think overall MyBib is effective as a reference manager software? *

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

9. After using mybib, did you get high scores for referencing part of the assessment criteria?

*

Yes

No

I don't know

10. Overall, are you satisfied with MyBib?

*

Very unsatisfied

1

2

3

4

5

Very satisfied

11. Have you used citation tools other than MyBib? *

Yes

No

12. What are they or what is it?

You can choose more than one option

*

Mendeley

Zotera

Endnote

Refworks

Other:

13. how do(does) they(it) compare to MyBib?

*

Far better than MyBib

Better than MyBib

The same as MyBib

Worse than MyBib

Far worse than MyBib

Appendix B

Figure 1

1. What is your gender?

33 responses

Figure 2

2. What is your age?

33 responses

Figure 3

3. What is your level?

33 responses

Figure 4

4. Have you used MyBib to create source references and citation for university assignments?

33 responses

Figure 5

5. How did you learn about MyBib? You can choose more than one option

23 responses

Figure 6

6. On a scale 1-5, how easy is it to use MyBib?

23 responses

Figure 7

7. On a scale 1-5, how would you assess the accuracy of MyBib for referencing and citation?

23 responses

Figure 8

8. Do you think overall MyBib is effective as a reference manager software?

23 responses

Figure 9

9. After using mybib, did you get high scores for referencing part of the assessment criteria?

23 responses

Figure 10

10. Overall, are you satisfied with MyBib?

23 responses

Figure 11

11. Have you used citation tools other than MyBib?

23 responses

Figure 12

12. What are they or what is it? You can choose more than one option

10 responses

Figure 13

13. how do(does) they(it) compare to MyBib?

10 responses

